

3D'omics outreach video 1

Deliverable 2.3

Month 23 (July 2023)

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General project information

Title	Three-dimensional holo'omic landscapes to unveil host-microbiota interactions shaping animal production
Acronym	3D'omics
Grant Agreement No.	101000309
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020
Instrument	RIA (Research and Innovation Action)
Project start date	01/09/2021
Duration of the project	48 months

Project partners

#	Partner	Abbrev	Type	Country
1	University of Copenhagen	UCPH	University	Denmark
2	Center for Genomic Regulation	CRG	Research Center	Spain
3	Veterinary University of Vienna	UVM	University	Austria
4	Max Delbrück Center	MDC	Research Center	Germany
5	KU Leuven	KUL	University	Belgium
6	ETH Zurich	ETH	University	Switzerland
7	Ben Gurion University	BGU	University	Israel
8	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NMBU	University	Norway
9	Afekta Technologies Limited	ATL	Industry, SME	Finland
10	Aviagen, Inc.	AVI	Industry	United Kingdom
11	Novogene Netherlands B.V.	NGE	Industry	The Netherlands
12	Biomin, GmbH	BIO	Industry	Austria
13	Norsvin SA	NOR	Industry	Norway

About this document

The original deliverable (D2.3) consisted of two explainer videos and the deadline was month 24. Due to the two functions of the videos (project introduction and dissemination of results), their delivery was split into two parts. The first video (described within this document) is about introducing the project and the technology we aim to develop. As it is the project presentation, an early delivery (M23) was decided in order to allow for maximum diffusion.

In an ongoing amendment process, it was requested that the second video will be a new deliverable (i.e., D2.8) to be published towards the end of the project (M42). The second explainer video will summarise the results of the project and ensure the accessibility of the concept of the newly developed technology to various interested parties.

Commission and concept for the video

After receiving and thoroughly reviewing proposals from three different companies, the video was finally commissioned to subcontractor Madeclear ApS, a production company based in Denmark.

This first explainer video introduces the project aims, the gaps in our knowledge, and current technical limitations. It further explains the main steps taken to achieve the project goal, highlights the societal impact, and lists the involved partners, as well as their role within the project. The final panel of the video shows the logos of all beneficiaries and acknowledges the funding through the European Commission.

Video location and dissemination

The video has been uploaded to the 3D'omics youtube channel and can be watched via this link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lo75rhOclkk>.

The video has also been shared via all of our social media channels as well as the social media outlets of the partner institutions. It is currently pinned on all 3D'omics platforms to allow for the widest possible reach of the video. The video has received over 180 views within the first 7 months of publication.

Video accessibility

The video contains sound (voice-over), as well as English subtitles. Automatic translation is enabled, so viewers can translate the subtitles into almost any language.